

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Complexes	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M Ω^{-1}
		Metal	NCO	NOS	Se		
1.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	20.20 (20.25)	28.60 (28.87)	—	—	4.87	2.8
2.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	18.90 (18.71)	25.55 (26.67)	—	—	4.95	0.8
3.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	16.30 (16.35)	23.25 (23.40)	—	—	5.00	3.2
4.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	18.20 (18.24)	—	35.82 (35.92)	—	4.97	2.1
5.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	16.85 (16.98)	—	33.20 (33.44)	—	5.21	1.6
6.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	15.12 (15.07)	—	29.50 (29.67)	—	5.11	2.5
7.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	14.22 (14.14)	—	—	37.95 (37.88)	5.00	2.0
8.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	13.42 (13.37)	—	—	35.70 (35.82)	4.90	4.2
9.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	12.30 (12.15)	—	—	32.90 (32.87)	4.95	4.8
10.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	22.10 (21.98)	28.20 (28.25)	—	—	—	5.0
11.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	20.10 (20.84)	26.00 (26.14)	—	—	—	3.4
12.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	18.00 (17.90)	27.25 (27.34)	—	—	—	4.6
13.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	19.96 (19.84)	—	35.00 (35.21)	—	—	2.8
14.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	18.30 (18.50)	—	32.00 (31.74)	—	—	2.0
15.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	16.30 (16.45)	—	29.25 (29.19)	—	—	1.2
16.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	15.82 (15.44)	—	—	37.00 (37.30)	—	4.0
17.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	14.50 (14.61)	—	—	35.10 (35.30)	—	3.2
18.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	13.10 (13.30)	—	—	32.00 (32.14)	—	1.6

bonded to the metal *via* terminal nitrogen⁴⁻⁷. The infrared spectra of the selenocyanate complexes exhibit a strong band at 2050-2090 and the medium intense band at 830-650 cm⁻¹ indicates terminally N-bonded selenocyanate group^{7,8}. The shift of of $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band from 3405-3380 in free diamines to 3320-3270 cm⁻¹ in complexes is the indication of coordination of diamines through nitrogen atom^{9,10}.

The Co^{II}-*o*-phenylenediamine complexes show two d-d bands at 8600-8950 and 18700-21900 cm⁻¹ suggesting octahedral geometry for the complexes¹¹. The complexes containing propylenediamine and diethylenediamine exhibit bands at 9300-9700 and 20500-22000 cm⁻¹, respectively, and are indicative of octahedral geometry¹² for the complexes.

References

1. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 12.
2. J. NELSON and S. M. NELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1597.
3. D. FORRESTER and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1286.
4. R. J. H. CLARK and C. M. WILLIAMS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 1081.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, 'Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds', John Wiley, New York, 1970, p. 188.
6. J. L. BURMISTER and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1587.

7. S. M. NELSON and T. M. SHEPHERD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 2125.
8. A. H. NORBURY, E. A. PYDER and R. F. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1439.
9. K. G. PATIL and E. D. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 645.
10. A. BRAIBANH, F. DALLAVALLE, M. A. PELLINGHELLI and E. LEPOZZI *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1430
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 824
12. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.

Uptake of Organic Acids by Weak Base Anion-exchange Resins

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THE uptake of organic acids by strong base anion-exchange resins has been studied¹⁻⁴ by many workers. Weak base anion-exchangers seem to

be less studied. Here, we present the results of our study on the uptake of eight carboxylic acids, viz. acetic, propionic, butyric, oxalic, tartaric, succinic and citric acids by two weak base gel-type anion-exchange resins, Tulsion WB and De Acidite HIP.

Experimental

Effect of concentration of equilibrating acid: Acetic, propionic, butyric, formic, oxalic, succinic, tartaric and citric acid solutions of four different concentrations, viz. 0.05, 0.12, 0.24 and 0.52 N were equilibrated using hydroxide forms of Tulsion WB and De Acidite HIP keeping the equilibration period constant at 24 h. The equilibrated solutions were analysed for the residual acidity. Results are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. (○) Acetic, (□) oxalic, (Δ) propionic, (●) citric, (×) butyric, (▼) succinic, (○) formic, and (⊙) tartaric acids; equilibrium temp. = 80°: (A) Tulsion WB resin, (B) De Acidite HIP resin.

Rate of uptake of organic acids: Air-dried resin (1 g) in the hydroxide, chloride and sulphate forms were equilibrated with 100 ml of 0.12 N acids. After a predetermined period of equilibration (ranging from 1 to 24 h) the samples of solutions were analysed for residual acidity. The adsorbed part of the uptake was determined by washing the resin with demineralised water. The results are presented graphically in Fig. 2. Constants a , a' , b and b' have been derived from the graphs.

Results and Discussion

It is seen from Fig. 2 that both the anion-exchange resins had rapid rate of uptake at the beginning followed by slower uptake. This system

corresponds to the surface exchange at first which is fast, and exchange later in the interior due to slow diffusion⁷. The total uptake of organic acids by Tulsion WB and De Acidite HIP was thus an exponential function of time and followed the equation, $y = bt^a$, where a and b are constants, y is the total uptake and t is the time in hours.

Fig. 2. (○) Acetic, (□) oxalic, (Δ) propionic, (●) citric, (×) butyric, (▼) succinic, (○) formic, and (⊙) tartaric acids, equilibrium temp. = 80°: (A) Tulsion WB resin, (B) De Acidite HIP resin.

The uptake of oxalic and citric acids by T.WB and of both dibasic and tribasic acids by De Acidite HIP was found to follow the Freundlich equation, $y = bc^a$, where a and b are constants, c is the concentration of acids (meq/100 ml) and y is the uptake of organic acids by resin (meq/g dry resin). This is in accordance with the results obtained by Robinson and Mills⁸ for the uptake of aliphatic acids by Duolite A anion-exchange resin. The values of constant a , were in the order, citric > oxalic for T.WB, and succinic > tartaric > citric > oxalic for De Acidite HIP.

The uptake of acetic, propionic, butyric, formic, succinic and tartaric acids by Tulsion WB and of the first four of the above six acids by De Acidite HIP follows a straight-line relation with concentration, $y = ac + b$, where y is the uptake of organic acids in meq/g dry resin, c is concentration of acid

in solution in meq/100 ml, and a and b are constants. The slopes for the different acids were in the order, butyric > formic > propionic > tartaric = succinic > acetic for Tulsion WB, and butyric > formic = propionic > tartaric for De Acidite HIP (Fig. 1).

Two more aspects of this study are also presented here.

Total uptake of organic acids by weak base anion-exchange resins in the hydroxide forms: It was found that the total uptake of monobasic organic acids by hydroxide forms of these two gel-type anion-exchange resins was in the order, butyric > propionic > acetic. This is in accordance with the results obtained by Robinson and Mills⁵ in their studies with the uptake of aliphatic acids by Duolite A-2 anion-exchange resin. The data also reveal that uptake of dibasic acids was in the sequence, oxalic > tartaric > succinic. The higher uptake of formic acid over the other monobasic acids, viz. acetic and propionic may be attributed to its high ionisation constant, 1.76×10^{-4} . Similarly, the higher uptake of oxalic and tartaric acids over that of succinic acid can be explained by their higher ionisation constants.

It was observed in the experiment that physical adsorption of oxalic acid was 0.7 meq/g dry resin for Tulsion WB and 0.2 meq/g dry resin for De Acidite HIP. Thus, these resins exhibited a capacity higher than their theoretical values when equilibrated with oxalic acid.

The higher uptake of citric acid on De Acidite HIP may be due to its physical adsorption. It is seen from the experiment that physical adsorption of this acid was 0.7 meq/g dry resin. Thus it can be concluded that the ionisation constant of organic acids plays an important role in their uptake by gel-type anion-exchange resins⁶. The magnitude of the effect of ionisation constant increases as the basicity of the resin decreases.

Uptake of organic acids by different forms of anion-exchange resins: It has been reported⁶ that relative ease of replacement of the various anions depends on valence, ion size and strength of acids formed by the anion, and that hydroxyl ion has a unique position in anion-exchange resins, e.g. hydroxyl ions exhibit an exceedingly high exchange potential. It is clear from the results presented that both the weakly basic anion-exchange resins under study have high exchange potential in their hydroxide forms over the chloride and sulphate forms in case of all the organic acids studied here. A similar observation was made by Trivedi⁶ during his studies on exchange equilibria of different anions on anion-exchange resins. It is for this reason of high exchange potential that effect of the concentration and rate of uptake have been studied here using hydroxide forms of both the resins.

References

1. U. N. RIZAEV and N. M. KAROL'KOV, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 6859.
2. A. P. KRISHKOV and E. N. SAYUSHEKINA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 63, 6859.

3. A. I. VALIKH, V. L. BOGATYREV and M. K. Z. KAYA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 68, 22946.
4. B. P. KRASHKOV and I. V. OVCHINNIKOVA, *Zh. Prikl. Khim.*, 1967, 40, 691 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, 67, 6026).
5. D. A. ROBINSON and G. F. MILLS, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, 41, 2221.
6. F. HELFFIRICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
7. O. B. AMPHLETT, "Inorganic Ionexchangers", Elsevier, New York, 1969.
8. R. KUNIN, "Ionexchange Resins", John Wiley, New York, 1968.
9. R. KUNIN and R. J. MYERS, *J. Phys. Colloid. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 5.
10. P. B. TRIVEDI, Ph. D. Thesis, Gujarat University, 1973.

Stability Constants of 2*N*-3,5-Dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole Complexes with Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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IN the present communication the dissociation constant of the 2*N*-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole and formation constant of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Bjerrum-Calvin^{1,2} pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³ at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at various ionic strengths in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The appropriate correction in all pH-meter readings were made on account of solvent as suggested by Van Uitert and Haas⁴.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligand: The ligand 2*N*-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1) was prepared by refluxing the equimolar quantities of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole with 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde in absolute alcohol for 3 h on a water-bath and was repeatedly crystallised in dioxane to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 218° (Found: C, 41.00; S, 7.00; N, 9.56. Calcd. C, 41.00; S, 7.28; N, 9.56%).

Materials: All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Standard solutions of copper sulphate and nickel sulphate were prepared in conductivity water.

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